

**KATHMANDU UNIVERSITY
SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING
DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING**

THESIS REPORT ON

**THERMAL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF NEW MODERN BUILDING
MATERIALS IN NEPAL – CASE STUDY OF THREE ECOLOGICAL ZONES USING
TRNSYS**

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the
Master of Engineering
in
Energy Efficient Building Design (EEBD)

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SEPTEMBER 2021

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THESIS EVALUATION

Thermal Performance Evaluation of New Modern Building Materials in Nepal - Case Study
of Three Ecological Zones Using TRNSYS

By

Ashok Sapkota

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my gratitude towards my Supervisors. I feel delighted about the fact that my supervisor **Prof. Bivek Baral** has been a character of admiration for me in all these years. I am grateful for his guidance and his valuable inputs during my Master's study and this thesis work. Prof. Baral has encouraged me to become a better person both academically and socially. I feel blessed to be guided by **Asst. Professor Tshewang Lhendup** for this research work. His inputs for this work are unmatched. I am thankful to him for the knowledge he gave to me regarding TRNSYS. Similarly, I am more than delighted to get a mentor like **Asst. professor Malesh Shah**. He has always helped me in my tough situations and motivated me. I feel proud to mention that he is my go-to person in any situation. He has guided me not only in this thesis work but in life also. His life lessons helped me evolve as a better person and take better decisions in life. He always treated me as a friend rather than his student.

I would like to express my special gratitude for **Prof. Hari Prasad Neopane** for his help and support. Initially, he encouraged me to get enrolled in this Master's course. I am always thankful to him for all the opportunities and exposure he provided me. Without his support, I wouldn't have been at this stage of my career.

I would like to express my thanks to **Asst. Professor Bijendra Shrestha** for his help during my course of study and this thesis work. He always encouraged me to perform better in my studies and work. He managed to find a solution for every problem I had with my study and guided me through it.

I would like to thank **Associate Prof. Daniel Tuladhar** for his help and support during my study period. Sincere gratitude to **Er. Sirapa Shrestha** and all the faculties of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kathmandu University for their helping hands.

I was involved in two different ERASMUS programs during my master's study. I was given chance to do a student Internship under the ERASMUS + (CIMCEB) program at Lund University, Sweden, and Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia. These experiences have given a new edge to my knowledge and I can bring that knowledge into this thesis work. Hence, I would like to thank the CIMCEB program, Lund University, and Tallinn University of Technology for the opportunity. I was selected as ERASMUS + exchange student at

Tuscia University, Italy under ERASMUS + exchange program and had an opportunity to study there. I would like to thank the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Tuscia University, and the ERASMUS office for helping and supporting me during my stay in Italy.

I would also like to thank University Grant Commission (UGC) and Kathmandu University for funding my study expenses through Formula Funding Scheme.

I express my special thanks to **Er. Nischal Chaulagain** for his help and inputs in this work. I am grateful for getting a friend like him and always enjoyed our discussion on energy-efficient building topics. I would like to thank my colleagues and classmates. Without all of them, this work wouldn't have been possible. Sincere thanks for **Er. Anuj Acharya** and **Er. Prarora Koirala** for their supporting hands throughout the study.

I would like to thank all the helping hands who contributed during the field visit and site survey. Thanks to all the house owners who participated during the survey and allowed me to study their building as my case study.

Last but not least I would like to convey my special gratitude to my family members. Without the support of my family, I wouldn't have been able to be here and do this research. Hence, they deserve all the credit.

ABSTRACT

Spending energy in a more efficient way is a wiser solution than finding new renewable sources of energy. During the quest for sustainable development, making sure that our buildings consume as little energy as possible is a vital step towards green and clean energy. One of the ways to make buildings energy efficient is the implantation of passive design techniques to buildings. Passive strategies take advantage of building architecture, environment, and materials to reduce its energy consumption. These techniques help to make the building more comfortable for residents and at the same time they reduce active energy demand.

Due to traditional hit-and-trial building construction practice and unavailability of sophisticated technology and materials, outdoor weather conditions seem to have severe effect on the indoor climate of building too. Passive techniques help in making the indoor thermal environment more comfortable and also reduce energy consumption if there is an active arrangement for thermal comfort. This research includes thermal performance evaluation of materials like AAC, CLT, PCM, sawdust brick, gypsum board, and cement board in three different climate regions of Nepal. Materials are applied at buildings located at subtropical, temperate and cold climates of Nepal with the help of TRNSYS. Additionally, the effect of other passive techniques such as thermal mass and building infiltration rate is incorporated with used material and results are analyzed.

Despite low energy demand, Dhanushadham building is found to be least improved by studied passive interventions. Building at Hile is heating dominant with a small cooling requirement. The existing energy demand of this building is slightly more than building at Dhanushadham. This building shows good improvement upon passive design implementations. It is found that more than 88% of energy demand of this building can be reduced by passive techniques considered by this research. Building at Lomanthang exhibited the maximum heating load with absence of cooling load. This building also showed good thermal improvement after passive technique implementation. It is found that more than 80% of existing building thermal energy consumption can be reduced with these materials along with other passive strategies. Most materials performance showed significant change with change in thickness. Higher thermal mass performs better compared to lower mass except for few conditions. Infiltration rate of one ACH which is a minimum value considered by the research is best suited for all construction types.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAC: Autoclaved Aerated Concrete

ACH: Air Change Hour

ASHRAE: American Society of Heating Refrigeration and Air-conditioning Engineers

ASTM: American Society of Testing and Materials

BCM: Building Construction Method

CB: Cement Board

CLT: Cross-laminated Timber

CMU: Cement Masonry Unit

CVRMSE: Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error

FHL: Fabric Heat Loss

GB: Gypsum Board

HEL: Heat energy loss

HVAC: Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning

KPH: Korean Passive House

LSL: Laminated Strand Lumber

m.a.s.l: Meters above Sea Level

NBM: New Building Material

NMBE: Normalizes Mean Biased Error

NRB: Nepalese Residential Building

PCM: Phase Change Material

PH: Passive House

PHPP: Passive House Planning Package

TEC: The Energy Conservatory

TES: Thermal Energy Storage

TRNSYS: TRaNsient SYstem Simulation program

USA: United States of America

LIST OF SYMBOLS

$^{\circ}\text{C}$: Degree Celsius

g/cm^3 : gram per cubic centimeter

J/KgK : Joule per Kilogram Kelvin

Kg/m^3 : Kilogram per cubic meter

KJ/KgK : Kilojoule per Kilogram Kelvin

Km : Kilometer

KW : Kilowatts

KWh/m^3 : Kilowatt hour per cubic meter of volume

$\text{KWh}/\text{m}^2.\text{yr}$: Kilowatt hour per square meter of floor area per year

m : meter

m^2 : Square meter

$\text{m}^3/\text{h}.\text{m}^2$: Cubic meter per hour per square meter of floor area

N/mm^2 : Newton per square millimeter

Pa : Pascal

USD/m^2 : US dollar per square meter of floor area

W : Watts

W/mK : Watts per meter Kelvin

$\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$: Watt per square meter Kelvin

W/m^2 : Watts per square meter of floor area

μm : micrometer

Ψ : Thermal conductivity at thermal bridge

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

A large amount of energy is consumed on buildings across the globe. Almost 40% of total global energy consumption is in the building sector [1]. The major portion of the energy consumption of residential as well as commercial buildings is on lighting and HVAC purpose. Household energy consumption in Nepal is focused more on lighting and cooking. Relatively less amount of energy is spent on HVAC systems as compared to other sectors like lighting and cooking [2]. The reason behind this is the lack of proper arrangement of external heating and cooling despite their high requirements. There are enough research and evidence that the indoor thermal environment is not comfortable enough and strongly needs an improvement in the case of the Nepalese Residential Building (NRB). In such a scenario, study on possibilities of maintaining indoor thermal comfort and making it in an energy-efficient way become one of the prominent fields of study.

1.1.1 Meteorological Background of Nepal

Nepal ranges between 26°22' to 30°27'N in latitude and 80°04' to 88°12'E in longitude. The country is approximately 885 km from east to west, 130 km to 260 km from north to south. Within this range, the altitudinal varies from approximately 60 m.a.s.l in the southern plain (called Terai) to Mount Everest (8848m) in the northeast. Because of topographic and physiographic variations over the country, Nepal features diverse climatic conditions. Based on thermal efficiency index and altitude, Nepal has 5 different climates namely tropical climate, mesothermal climate, microthermal climate, taiga, and tundra concerning thermal efficiency index. The thermal efficiency index is calculated based on air temperature and precipitation [3]–[5]. Different climate variation based on this index is shown in Figure 1.

S. Bodach, 2014 has performed an analysis of a bioclimatic chart of 26 different locations of Nepal. Results led to a classification of Nepal into 4 different bioclimatic zones [6]. They are:

1. Warm Temperate (below 500 m.a.s.l.)
2. Temperate (501-1500 m.a.s.l.)
3. Cool Temperate (1501-2500 m.a.s.l.)
4. Cold (above 2500 m.a.s.l.)

Figure 1: Classification of Climates of Nepal [5]

Annual maximum average temperature ranges from 18°C to 36°C depending on different climate zone. Similarly, the annual minimum average temperature varies from 6°C to 18°C throughout the country [3]. Moreover, understanding temperature variation at the same place in different seasons is also important to get an idea about indoor and outdoor thermal conditions.

Nepal mainly has 4 seasons. They are winter (ranging between December to February), pre-monsoon (ranging between March to May), monsoon (ranging between June to September), and post-monsoon (ranging between October to November) [7]. Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate average minimum and average maximum temperatures during winter and summer (monsoon) seasons. It is evident from the figures that temperatures can go extreme during both hot and cold seasons.

Figure 2: Winter Average Minimum Temperature of Nepal [7]

Figure 3: Summer Average Maximum Temperature of Nepal [7]

Several studies have found similar results about the climates and temperatures of Nepal. Generally, air temperature near the surface goes extreme during winter and summer (during pre-monsoon and early monsoon) [8]. ASHRAE has defined thermal comfort as a perception of the mind. It also stated that thermal comfort varies from person to person. Comfort condition depends on individual physiological and psychological variation. However, at around 24°C, the human mind tends to feel satisfied and comfortable in terms of the thermal

environment around it [9]. As the outdoor temperature can go to an extreme during both summer and winter, it affects the indoor temperature too. These temperatures do not satisfy the comfort range defined by standards. Closer observation towards temperature variation throughout the country across all seasons is required to know about the building's indoor quality in detail. It will help to draw a comparison of real indoor conditions with standard comfort conditions.

Table 1: Season-wise Temperature Variation and Rainfall in Nepal [7]

S No	Season	Temperature Variation Across Country (°C)		Rainfall (mm)	
		Average Minimum	Average Maximum	Minimum	Maximum
1	Winter	-2 to 12	12 to 24	25	200
2	Pre-Monsoon	4 to 20	18 to 36	50	350
3	Monsoon	12 to 26	24 to 36	500	4500
4	Post-Monsoon	2 to 18	18-30	0	200

Table 1 demonstrates temperature variation and rainfall in different seasons throughout Nepal. It is interesting to see the range of temperatures during winter and summer (pre-monsoon and monsoon). Several parts of the country demand heating arrangement during winter. Additionally, the temperature goes much above the comfort range in some parts of the country during summer. It indicates that there is cooling demand too during pre-monsoon and monsoon season.

Table 2: Temperature Variation in Different Regions of Nepal [7]

Season	Temperature Range (°C)	Climatic Region		
		Subtropical	Temperate	Cold
Winter	Average Maximum	20 to 24	16 to 22	12 to 16
	Average Minimum	8 to 12	4 to 8	-2 to 4
Summer	Average Maximum	32 to 36	26 to 32	24 to 28
	Average Minimum	24 to 26	16 to 22	2 to 18

Table 2 illustrates the average recorded temperature variation in different climate regions. The average temperature does not go beyond 24°C during winter but comes down as low as -

2°C. Especially northern part of the country (Cold region) measures much cooler as compared to southern subtropical regions. The average minimum temperature in all 3 regions is relatively lower than comfort temperature as defined by standards. In contrast, the average maximum temperature remains within a tolerable limit in cold climates during summer. The other two regions (subtropical and temperate) exceed the comfort range during summer and are expected to require cooling during summer. Previous researchers have also concluded that Nepal has a variety of climates despite its small size. Subtropical to arctic climates can be experienced in different altitudes ranging between 60 m.a.s.l to 8848 m.a.s.l [10].

1.1.2 Present Condition of Buildings in Nepal

Past research works have found that indoor air temperature is not in the comfort range both during summer and winter. Excessive openness through windows and doors makes Nepalese buildings either excessively hot or excessively cold during extreme weather. An increase in the use of modern materials such as concrete and glass makes our buildings even more uncomfortable [10].

According to a survey conducted in the year 2015/16, 86.5 % of the total residents responded that they live in their own house. 96.3 % family in rural areas and 72.1 % family in urban areas reside in their own house. Similarly, 98.4 % household of the poorest quartile is found to be living in their own house [11]. We can conclude that residents in Nepal like to build their own houses for residence. Traditional Nepalese house design has been based on rural material. The traditional construction and design are based on the availability of skill of manpower and materials which might be very limited especially in rural areas. These construction practices are concentrated on simplistic approaches. The preferred BCMs are mud and tile system in a central hilly region, stone, and boulder with minutely ventilated small houses in mountains, and bamboo, mud, and straw-thatched huts in hotter terai [12], [13].

As of 2015/16, 60.4% of outer walls in urban buildings are found to be made of cement-bonded stone/brick. In contrast, mud bonded brick/stone walls were 49.3% in rural buildings with only 20.4% with cement-bonded stone/brick. However, cement bonded brick/stone walls percentage can be expected to increase slightly higher because of the reconstruction of many earthquake-destroyed buildings in recent years. Major materials used for roofing purposes in Nepal are galvanized iron sheets, concrete roofing, and tiles/slate roofs. Galvanized iron sheets are more popular in rural areas and concrete roofing in urban areas[11].

Materials used in building construction play a vital role in its energy interaction with the surrounding which further governs building overall energy demand. Building materials perform important roles in supporting, insulating and making the building airtight. Materials help to control temperature and humidity inside a building [14]. Hence, it is very important to see possible enhancement and improvement in building materials that are more suitable for Nepalese climates. It is also very important to evaluate the performance of new materials that are available in the market but is underused in our buildings.

1.2 Problem Statement

It is evident that climates in different regions of Nepal can go to extreme conditions during both summer and winter. Such extreme outdoor climate can result in an uncomfortable indoor environment. This issue needs to be addressed as soon as possible because the indoor comfort level is directly connected with occupant health too.

Materials used in different sections of a building directly affect its indoor behavior. The material used in the facade, roof and foundation plays a vital role in its energy interaction with the surrounding environment determining the indoor climate of a building.

Residents still rely on very few traditional construction materials. Indoor thermal comfort level can be enhanced through smart selection of material. Better performing material can reduce active heating and cooling which reduces carbon footprint of the building [15]. Thermal performance analysis of new building materials in context of Nepalese climates is important to inspect the possibilities to improve indoor environment and energy efficiency. It's necessary to evaluate performances of materials and best suited climate for their application before jumping into new solutions.

1.3 Objectives

The main aim of this research is to evaluate the thermal performance of new modern building materials in different climates of Nepal. The general objectives of this study are as follows:

- To study present thermal comfort situation in Nepalese residential buildings
- To identify improved building materials that might apply to specific Nepalese climate regions
- To evaluate the thermal performance of existing materials and compare them with new materials
- To study the effect of passive techniques for different climates of Nepal and find the best solution combining passive techniques with choice of material

1.4 Scope of Research

- Many materials are gaining popularity as improved materials in the international market but are rarely used in the Nepalese construction industry. Few such materials are applied in case study buildings located in different regions of Nepal.
- Three buildings are chosen in three climate zones as a case study in this research. Selection of buildings is influenced by climate region, construction material, local settlement and economic background.
- The effect of passive techniques such as thermal mass and infiltration rate on the indoor thermal environment incorporated with NBMs is studied in this research.
- The results of this study are in a form of indoor temperatures of buildings and annual heating and cooling demands.
- Results of this research can be used by building designers, architectures, policy makers and government agencies
- Heating set point and cooling set point is set as 18°C and 24°C respectively for calculation of heating and cooling demand

1.5 Limitations

- Only a few materials are chosen as new materials. Thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity and density of materials are directly taken either from literature review or from the manufacturer manual.
- Buildings chosen for this study are taken each as a case study that represents one particular climate zone. However, there are many other types of building designs in the same zone whose performance may differ from studied building.
- During simulation of buildings, occupants and internal heat gains are taken into consideration purely based on a questionnaire survey during a site visit.
- Weather data used in this study are taken from Meteonorm software. Data calculated by the software may contain some inaccuracy which might cause errors in the result of the study.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Thermal Comfort Scenario of Residential Buildings in Nepal

Residents have to face uncomfortable environments both indoor and outdoor during the extremely hot and cool season in Nepal. Although they seem to adjust with the environment, still indoor temperature lies beyond the comfort range defined by standards. Rijal *et al.* 2001 have found that room temperature during nighttime in cold climates falls well below comfort temperature [10]. The energy was found to be lost through the walls and roof of a building. Because of socio-economic reasons, residents sleep on the floor in many parts of the country. Residents were found to feel discomfort because of low surface temperature while sleeping in earthen rooms [16].

The indoor air temperature of NRBs falls very low, especially during winter. Even if residents tend to adjust to lower temperatures, they feel uncomfortable in all climatic regions of the country. Gautam *et al.* 2019 have measured mean indoor globe temperature during winter in their study. Temperature is found to be 12.2 °C, 16.9 °C and 22.2 °C in cold, temperate and subtropical climates respectively. Mean comfort temperature is also calculated based on thermal comfort survey which is found to be lower than specified in international standards in all climate regions [17].

The building sector in Nepal has adopted conventional building design and construction techniques across the country. This is mainly because of the availability of limited and similar building materials all over the country. Traditional buildings tend to provide better thermal comfort as compared to modern dwellings [18], [19]. Despite this fact, the Nepalese building industry has rapidly adopted the modern design in urban areas. As a result of this, our buildings need energy-intensive mechanical arrangements for thermal comfort. Because of family prestige and the limitation of designers and architectures, buildings that are made in urban areas are seen to be copied to rural areas also. Similarly, a building that is suitable for one region is also being adopted in another region which is not suitable there. This causes an unacceptable indoor comfort level inside a residence even though buildings are modern [6]. However, researches have also shown that some traditional buildings tend to be uncomfortable in winter and need some modification to achieve acceptable thermal comfort condition [20]–[22].

During summer and winter, the outdoor temperature reaches extreme in a subtropical region of Nepal. Summer is very hot whereas winter becomes cold. To maintain natural ventilation, traditional dwellings are more open. The ratio of opening area to total envelope area is large. These openings are permanent and cannot be fixed during winter also. Such openings cause an extremely cold environment during winter. People living in the subtropical climate of Nepal face extreme weather conditions. Their buildings are not sophisticated and do not possess mechanical temperature controlling arrangements. Each year people suffer extreme heat during summer resulting in discomfort and illness which leads to death also. People living in warm climates have a higher degree of comfort temperature as compared to people living in a cool climate. This is because people are forced to adjust to extreme weather and they develop adaptive measures [8].

Nepalese traditional buildings are highly influenced by outdoor weather conditions. A similar effect can be experienced during winter. In winter temperature falls to extreme cold throughout Nepal [7]. Extreme outdoor temperature reflects in the indoor environment too. The indoor environment of vernacular buildings is highly determined by outdoor climate [23]. Because of this effect of outdoor temperature, houses become extremely chilled. Both traditional and modern buildings are also highly affected by an external environment. Research has found that the minimum surface temperature of walls and roofs of concrete houses is much lower than those of vernacular houses [19]. This way, both traditional and residential buildings are not comfortable during winter in almost all regions of the country.

According to a study conducted by Shrestha *et al.* 2020, indoor temperatures of school buildings in Nepal are found similar to outdoor temperature [24]. As the outdoor environment can go from extreme hot to extreme cold all over the country, it can be stated that the indoor environment of school buildings in Nepal can be extreme. Extreme thermal conditions can affect students' concentration and their effectiveness in learning. Thermal discomfort can cause irritation, tiredness, illness and serious health problems to students [25]. There is a high possibility of a rise in health issues to children as well as an adult in the residential building too.

Evaluation of building thermal comfort can be done by knowing how much energy is being consumed by a building or the extent of mechanical device uses given that outside temperature is in extreme condition. Nepal ranks on the list of least energy-consuming countries in the world in terms of building services. The use of mechanical devices to control indoor air quality and temperature is still very low in the country [2]. When the indoor temperature is already beyond comfort level and mechanical arrangements are rarely used

then residents adjust themselves to the environment. Residents still rely on traditional and primitive techniques to adjust themselves to extreme climatic conditions. The average measured temperature was found to be 10.9°C, 18°C and 20°C in cold, temperate and subtropical climates. These temperatures are below the range of the average calculated comfort temperature for each climatic region [26]. A study done by Pokhrel *et al.* 2020, states that 90% of the measured indoor air temperature is below average comfort temperature across 3 different climate zones of Nepal [27].

Researchers have also conducted a case study-based investigation to determine the thermal status of the indoor climate of Nepalese buildings. Although their results do not represent the entire countries' scenario but provide insight into the present condition of certain buildings in specific climate zones. Thapa *et al.* 2018 studied the indoor thermal comfort level of temporary shelters made after the massive earthquake in 2015. A study finds that residents do not feel comfortable and prefer to make shelters warmer during winter and cooler during summer. Mean indoor temperature among all studied shelters varies between 12.1°C to 18.5°C during winter and 26.9°C to 33.2°C during summer [28]. Chaulagain *et al.* 2019 also performed simulation-based research on buildings located at Biratnagar and Dhulikhel. Results conclude that indoor comfort level is not suitable for residents based on hourly temperature calculated inside buildings. Results also illustrate that the building in Biratnagar is overheated for more than 6 months whereas the building at Dhulikhel is underheated for more than 4 months [29].

2.2 Passive House- Climate Responsive Building Concept

Passive houses are mainly characterized by their less embodied energy consumption. The embodied energy of a building can be defined as the total energy demand of a building from its construction to demolition. Although construction of PHs costs 5%-10% additionally, their embodied energy remains comparatively less. Passive Houses (PHs) are those buildings that use a minimal amount of energy for heating and cooling applications. To be precise, PHs account for only less than 15 kWh/m².yr of energy for heating and cooling purpose. Such houses normally consume less than 80%-90% energy as compared to conventional buildings. Passive house is mainly concerned with high insulation, airtightness and controlled ventilation. PH is more driven by quality and comfort. In other words, PH achieves acceptable quality inside the house with a minimal amount of energy consumption. There are few passive components of a building that help in the reduction of active heating and cooling. Such components are insulation, orientation benefits, heat recovery and air-tight envelope.

PH requires very less amount of energy for heating, ventilation and air condition (HVAC) purposes. PH can be considered as optimization of building design taking into consideration of local climate conditions. From the building construction phase to demolition, the operational phase is the most important phase of its life cycle in terms of its impact on the environment. In this regard, it's very important to construct a building in such a way that it consumes as little energy as possible during its operational phase. PH concept deals with taking benefits from climate and local weather. Therefore passive houses are also referred to as climate-responsive buildings [30]–[36].

Rangel 2021 studied the evolution and impact of PH concepts through archival research. Climate-responsive building design concepts were initiated from cold European countries. The first attempt was to reduce space heating energy by enhancing the U values of a building envelope. Later these concepts were adapted to other different parts of the world where climates are different from Europe but found to be equally beneficial. Few examples are Mexico, China, the USA and Chile where climates other than cold can be experienced. Common difference between PH and the conventional house is presented in Table 3 in terms of building properties [34].

Table 3: Constructional Parameters for Passive House and Non-passive House [34]

Parameter	Air Tightness	Wall U- value	Roof U- value
Passive House	0.05 m ³ /h.m ² at 50 Pa	0.03 W/m ² K	0.04 W/m ² K
Non Passive House	1.3 m ³ /h.m ² at 50 Pa	0.14 W/m ² K	0.10 W/m ² K

Researchers have suggested and evaluated a variety of design approaches for different climates around the world. Lee et al. 2020 studied Korean low-energy buildings also called Korean Passive House (KPH). The study finds that KPH has been constructed based on climate responsive design and used locally available materials. Through simulation, the result reveals that KPH is more energy-efficient as compared to conventional Korean houses [30].

Schnieders et al. 2015 conclude through their research that passive houses can be constructed in any climate of the world. The results presented demonstrate that architectural design should not be compromised while designing a climate-responsive building. Important components of a building such as a window, door, wall, insulation, mechanical services as well as building shape and orientation can be designed based on the local climate. The researchers state that even for passive houses, annual cooling demand might exceed 70 KWh/m² for a hot and humid place [32].

Climate responsive building constructed by Dan *et al.* 2016 following PH criteria at temperate climate region of Romania is monitored for its overall energy demand. Construction of the building is carried out taking into consideration of Romanian local climate, material and construction technology. Research shows a clear improvement in energy demand and the life cycle cost of a building. Real-time monitoring of energy demand and indoor parameters shows that the building satisfies all criteria for PH. The primary energy demand of a building is found as less than 120 kWh/m² for a year. Indoor temperature is found to be comfortable during all seasons with slightly overheating during summer [35].

The construction of climate-responsive houses is generally associated with technical and financial challenges. Martinez *et al.* 2020 performed a technical and financial feasibility study of PH in various climates of Chile. They mention in their result that energy demand will sharply increase if energy efficiencies in buildings are not considered in the future. The research concludes that passive house contributes to the reduction of heating demand in Chile by 85% and also reduces CO₂ by 60% during its operational phase. In Chile, the construction of a building satisfying PH standards costs 640 USD/m². Results show that meeting PH standards for building construction are feasible and within the limit of Chilean housing subsidy. However, floor area might be compromised in cold climates [37]. These results are relatable in the context of Nepal also.

Climate responsive buildings can be constructed in hot and humid as well as subtropical climates also. Dalbem *et al.* 2016 attempted to verify PH design strategies in humid subtropical climates of southern Brazil. The architectural design is made following the guidelines and design principles of PH incorporated with the local climate. The energy balance of a building is done by using the PHPP tool (Passive House Planning Package). Results conclude that it is possible to meet PH goals following PH design principles in subtropical climates of Brazil. Parameters like primary energy demand, heating & cooling load and overheating of buildings are found to be within the limit defined by PH guidelines and certification criteria [38]. Fokaides *et al.* 2016 evaluated the performance of energy-efficient buildings constructed in a subtropical climate. The study is based on monitoring the performance of a building constructed in Cyprus which is designed and constructed following PH design criteria and guidelines. Rooms for improvement in a building are seen even though the overall performance is improved. For example, overheating problems are identified for some hours during summer. This problem is also found to be solved in some way by optimizing the strategy of night ventilation. Results conclude that night ventilation can decrease the temperature by 1.4 °C [39].

Figueiredo *et al.* 2016 investigated the possibilities of making PH in the context of Portuguese climate. Results show that there is a possibility for reduction of heating and cooling demand along with overheating rate by 62%, 72% and 4.4% respectively. Additionally, the study concludes that there is a possibility of satisfying PH requirements for steel structured building at Portuguese climate [40]. Similar work has been done by Huang *et al.* 2020. Their study includes finding possibilities of converting an existing multi-story building to PH employing retrofitting. The study finds that the total energy demand of case study building reduces by 78.9% following the retrofitting with PH standards. Result also projects that the payback period of cost of PH standard retrofitting is approximately 18 years [41].

Performance of PH is largely affected by non-constructural factors like occupant behavior. Certified PH still has room for improvement. Besides, continuous maintenance is also required on a building to keep its energy demand within the permissible limit. K. Was *et al.* 2020 present the experimental result of the annual energy demand of a building (already certified as PH) in their work. Prefabricated lightweight passive house which is located in southern Poland is monitored throughout its operational time from 2011-2019. Results presented show that heating energy demand is within the limit of the value required for PH criteria. However, total primary energy demand is found to be well above the limit from the second year of operation itself. The study also identifies that it's because of occupant habit and operation of a building. The research concludes that PH is vulnerable to human impact and source of energy and there might be room for maintenance during its operational phase to regain PH standard [42].

2.2.1 Passive House Principles and Design Criteria

As defined by Rangel 2020 [43], there are 5 different principles of PH.

1. Super Insulation
2. Thermal bridge free construction
3. Airtight building envelopes
4. Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery
5. High-performance door and window

The standard PH requires a very low U value to all envelopes of a building. It should be less than $0.15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$. Thermal bridges must have a value ψ (Ψ) lower than 0.01 W/(mK) for PH certification. Glass, the window frames and installation should have a $0.85 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ or

lower thermal transmittance value. A building must have an infiltration value of 0.6 ACH at 50 Pa measured by a blower door test to get certified. PH normally should have a heat recovery efficiency of more than 75%. The primary energy demand of PHs should not be more than 120 KWh/m² whereas heating and cooling demand should not exceed 15 KWh/m². PHs mostly rely on passive cooling during the hot season. There might be some issue of overheating. The indoor temperature must not exceed 25°C for more than 10% of the year. A limit of 20% is permissible for climates with a humidity ratio of more than 12g/Kg [36], [44].

2.3 Role of Materials in Building Performance

The building sector uses a large number of materials from its construction to demolition. In Europe itself, the average material extracted from the earth for building purposes is 4.8 tons per inhabitant per year. Normally materials used in a building contribute to 50% of embodied energy of a building. Choosing materials with high energy consumption intensity will affect the energy balance and thermal performance of a building and also makes environmental impacts. These facts indicate that building planners and designers should be very careful about choosing the right materials for building construction because they will determine buildings' embodied energy consumption. It is expected that much of building growth will come from developing nations where energy regulations are not yet prioritized. Projections predict that by 2050, 170 billion square meters of floor area will be constructed out of which 100 billion square meters will be without considering energy performance regulations. In the coming days too, materials will play a vital role in determining overall building energy performance because materials are an important aspect of the building phenomenon. Different materials are used in different parts of a building envelope. The facade, roof, foundation, window and door are building elements that are responsible for energy interaction between the building and the outside environment. Materials used in these building sections play a vital role in determining the amount of energy exchanged between indoor and outdoor climates. Designing a building with materials with appropriate properties for a particular climate condition is always important. Advancement in building materials can help to reduce the energy demand of a building, make a building more comfortable and help to mitigate the environmental impact of buildings. There are many opportunities to enhance building performance and sustainability through material advancement. Performance of wall, roof, window and door can be improved through better material selection. The smart selection of material looking at thermal insulation and thermal storage capacity which is suitable for given climate conditions gives immense benefits to building overall thermal

performance Selection of building material for various sections depends on surrounding climate, usage pattern of building, and building type [45]–[47].

Heat energy loss (HEL) is energy transferred between the building and surrounding. This phenomenon determines the indoor thermal behavior of the building. HEL occurs in two ways. The first one is fabric heat loss (FHL) and the second one is ventilation loss. Fabric loss is heat exchange that occurs through the walls, roof, foundation, door and window of a building. Najjar *et al.* 2019 found in their study that fabric heat loss accounts for 81% of total HEL and concludes that material used in a building plays a vital role in HEL. Results demonstrates that the percentage of improvement in the U value of building material is directly proportional to the reduction in HEL [48]. The proper and precise choice of material and its properties is an important factor to reduce the overall HEL of a building. Materials are considered a passive element of a building. They support building and also act as a thermal barrier between indoor and outdoor climates. They act to buffer the temperature and humidity in a space. There are plenty of opportunities to reduce environmental impact as well as enhance building comfort level through the advancement of materials. The use of eco-friendly materials with low thermal conductivity will make buildings better and decreases greenhouse emissions. The selection of best-suited materials reduces the overall energy demand of a building and also contributes to reducing the carbon footprint of the building industry worldwide [14], [45], [49]–[51]. Figure 4 illustrates FHL in a typical building given by Najjar *et al.*

Figure 4: Percentage Breakdown of FHL in Building [48]

Materials that are supposed to be used in a building should have some specific properties. They should possess high thermal resistance. In other words, the material should be able to resist heat transmission at the minimum possible thickness. Researches have shown that indoor thermal quality is still a concern in many underdeveloped and developing countries. Discomfort inside residents is common in many countries across the globe. In such a situation application of improved material can enhance comfort quality. Material with high thermal resistance, good moisture control and good structural properties are useful for improving building's overall performance. The amount of material also helps to maintain building comfort. High thermal mass is beneficial when used in the specific climate in the right quantity [47].

2.3.1 Commonly Used Materials

Varieties of materials are used in a building construction around the world. Choice of a material depends on the climate, traditional and cultural values, type and use of a building, type of settlement, economical background, availability of material, etc. The selection of materials also depends upon their application and their properties. Table 4 presents commonly used building materials along with their application and standout properties [49].

Table 4: Commonly Used Building Materials

Name of Material	Building Application	Applied Climate	Special Properties
Cork Insulation	insulation material	the cold climate of Europe	low thermal conductivity
Wood and Timber	window, door, roof, floor, facade	almost every climate but more used in a cold climate	hygroscopic material with a high specific capacity, low conductivity and low density
Straw	facade and insulation	cold climate	high thermal resistance
Rockwool Insulation	insulation	cold climate	has capability to obstruct sound and heat propagation
Brick	facade element	every climate	high specific heat
Fly Ash Brick	facade element	every climate	low conductivity
Concrete	facade, roof and foundation	every climate	high heat storage, high thermal mass
Aerated Autoclaved Concrete (AAC)	facade element	every climate	high heat storage and low conductivity
Vermiculite Concrete	insulation	cold and hot climate	low conductivity
Extruded Polystyrene Foam	insulation	cold and hot climate	low conductivity
Phase Change Material (PCM)	added with concrete, brick and gypsum boards on walls and ceiling	every climate	high heat storage
Vacuum Insulation Panel	insulation	cold and hot climate	low conductivity
Roof Tiles	roofing	every climate	high solar reflectivity
Bamboo	facade and roofing	subtropical climate	cheaply available

2.4 Building Energy Modelling and Simulation

Before the computer age, building designers and architectures used to rely on manual design and calculation. Strong computer performance and their capability of executing calculations at rapid speed have laid the foundation for computer-based building designing. Computer-based energy simulation of a building is linked with optimized building design as well as energy-efficient operation. Simulation provides a better understanding of design decisions and their direct impact on building energy scenarios. This knowledge helps in improving design and develops operational strategies [52]. Energy requirements of a building largely depend on the performance of individual elements of the building such as wall, roof, window, door and lighting arrangement. Moreover, performance is also a combination of all single parameters as one unique system. It is important to study building as a single entity combining all individual parameters. To design an optimized performance combination, energy simulation tools are very essential. Such tools help to design a more efficient building which acts as a system [53].

Computer-based energy performance simulation have played important role in the development of energy-efficient building designs and techniques. Building can be modeled in a build condition and its performance can be evaluated for similar climatic conditions as outdoor by means of simulation software. From a designer's perspective, energy modelling and performance tolls have helped them to know the consequence of their design. They can see the effect of a new design idea before proceeding to construction. This process enormously helps to develop new ideas and policies. New materials are being developed and being evaluated before their application in the real constructional field. Physical characteristics of such innovation are possible to represent in a model and their output can be analyzed [54], [55].

2.4.1 Building Energy Simulation in Nepalese Buildings

Building energy simulation tools are used in various studies related to Nepalese buildings. Authors have shown the application of such tools through their results and recommendations. The energy demand of existing buildings in different cases is compared with possible improved solutions. Bergquist, 2016 has researched improving the indoor air quality of residential buildings of Nepal at different locations. Building thermal performance and energy demands are calculated with different possible passive techniques using building energy simulation software [56]. Similarly, Shrestha 2017 has evaluated energy consumption and thermal comfort scenarios of buildings in Kathmandu. SIMIEN simulation software is

used for energy calculation of existing and modified buildings. The study proposes several passive strategies for better thermal comfort levels at minimal energy demand through simulation. Similar research is done by Kandel 2019 with consideration of modern and traditional buildings located at subtropical climates as case study. Energy simulation of existing and retrofitted buildings are done in ida-ice software [57], [58]. Additionally, Chaulagain 2020 also examined the thermal behavior and energy demand of existing buildings in different locations of Nepal. The study also evaluates the effect of implementing selected passive techniques in an existing building through EnergyPlus software. EnergyPlus is also used by Yadav *et al.* 2017 in their research which includes energy demand calculation of a supermarket located in Kathmandu. Research also evaluates the improvement of building performance upon implementing passive techniques in the building [59], [60].

Many techniques and ideas which potential to improve building energy demand and indoor environment comfort level. In context of Nepal with huge climatic variations, these techniques might have contrasting outcome from one region to another region. Particularly selected technique can be effective at one specific climate but not so effective at another. It is very important to study the best-suited design strategies for every climate variation. This analysis is very easy with help of computer tools and software. The applicability and effectiveness of such techniques can be studied through building energy simulation software.

2.4.2 TRNSYS as Building Simulation Software

TRNSYS (also known as TRaNsient SYstem Simulation program) is a simulation environment for the simulation of transient systems. This program is used by engineers, designers and researchers around the world. TRNSYS is a very powerful tool for simulating simple hot water systems to multi-zone buildings.

Applications of TRNSYS [61]

- Central Plant Modelling
- Building Simulation
- Solar Thermal Processes
- Ground Coupled Heat Transfer
- High-Temperature Solar Application
- Geothermal Heat Pump System
- Coupled Multi-zone Thermal/Airflow Modelling
- Optimization

- Energy System Research
- Emerging Technology Assessment
- Power Plants (Biomass, Cogeneration)
- Hydrogen Fuel Cell Systems
- Wind and Photovoltaic Systems
- Data and Simulation Calibration

Building simulation is done in TRNSYS through TRNBuild. Constructional details of buildings and specifications are provided in TRNBuild. Additionally, Physical structure and thermal behaviors of a building like heating and cooling schedules are defined in TRNBuild. Further simulation procedures are executed in the simulation studio.

CHAPTER III: METHODS

This research work is conducted by performing different tasks at different stages of studies to achieve its objectives. Key tasks that are performed during this research are divided in three categories. They are literature review, field survey and computer simulation. Literature review includes the works related to background study and problem identification. Study of different climate zone, building types, materials and site selection are included in literature review. Questionnaire survey, detail specification study of case study building and occupant survey are conducted during field survey. All computers based modelling and simulation is performed during third stage of the research. Overall work flow of the research is presented in Figure 5. Various stages of research are displayed in a figure according to their occurrence and execution.

Figure 5: Overall Work Flow of Research

3.1 Site Selection

Certain criteria are taken into consideration while selecting the case study buildings in this research. Those criteria are:

1. Climate zone
2. Construction type
3. Material selection
 - Facade material
 - Roof material
 - Floor material
 - Window/Door material
4. Other Criteria (active heating and cooling, willingness to retrofit, financial background, etc.)

3.1.1 Climate Zone

Literature research shows that the climates of Nepal are divided into different zones based on a variety of factors. Bioclimatic variations have resulted in a division of Nepalese climate into 4 different regions. Similarly, 5 climates are defined in Nepal based on the thermal efficiency index [5], [6]. The majority of research works related to thermal comfort and energy-efficient building strategies are found to be conducted in three climate belts of Nepal. Those regions are Terai (subtropical) region, the Hilly (temperate) region and the Himalayan (cold) region. Thermal performance evaluation of buildings and thermal perception studies are also conducted in these three zones. Similarly, some researchers have developed passive design strategies in these three different regions considering climate variation and other factors [16], [17], [23], [24], [26]–[29]. This study has also considered three climate variations in Nepal leading to a selection of case study buildings accordingly.

3.1.2 Construction Type and Material

Three varieties of human settlements can be observed in Nepal. They are mainly urban, semi-urban and rural settlements. Differences in result variations in construction practices also. Construction practice and technology are found to be different in rural, semi-urban and urban areas during the field study which is conducted as a part of this research. It is observed that cement-bonded brick construction with concrete roofing construction is highly common in urban areas. Similarly, mud bonded stone structure with GI sheet roofing is found as the

preferred structure in rural areas. Cement bonded stone structures are also observed in semi-urban settlement. Figure 6 shows earthen laminated bamboo type wall construction seen in Dhanushadham in southern Nepal. Figure 7 represents concrete wall construction in Kathmandu. Similarly, Figure 8 shows mud bonded stone wall building seen in Terathum district in eastern hilly region of Nepal.

Figure 6: Typical Bamboo Earthen House

Figure 7: Cement Bonded Brick with Concrete Roofing Type Building

Figure 8: Mud Bonded Stone Wall Type Building

Table 5 demonstrates the type of wall material and roof material applied across Nepal. Data show that cement-bonded brick/stone wall and mud bonded brick/stone wall is the most common construction types throughout the country. Furthermore, Galvanized iron sheet roof and concrete roof are two of the highest preferred roofing in Nepal [11].

Table 5: Percentage Use of Wall Material and Roof Material in Nepal

Type of roofing	Total usage (%)	Material for the outer wall	Total usage (%)
Galvanized iron sheet	33.9	Cement bonded brick/stone	36.6
Concrete roofing	28.8	Mud bonded brick/stone	37.6
Tiles and slate roof	22.6	Wood	4.7
Straw/thatch	11.3	Bamboo	14.7
Wood plank	0.9	Unbacked brick	1.2
Earth mud	1.1	Other	5.1
Other	1.4		

Table 6: Wall Type in Urban and Rural areas [11]

	Cement bonded brick/stone	Mud bonded brick/stone	Wood	bamboo/leaves	Unbacked bricks	Other materials	Total
Urban (%)	60.4	20.4	4.3	11.1	1.3	2.4	100.0
Rural (%)	20.4	49.3	5.0	17.1	1.2	7.0	100.0
Nepal (%)	36.6	37.6	4.7	14.7	1.2	5.1	100.0

Table 7: Roof Type in Urban and Rural Areas [11]

	Concrete/cement	Galvanized iron	Wood/planks	Tiles/slate	Straw/thatch	Earth/mud	Other	Total
Urban (%)	48.9	31.3	1.2	13.5	5.0	0.0	0.2	100
Rural (%)	15.2	35.5	0.7	28.7	15.6	1.8	2.3	100
Nepal (%)	28.8	33.9	0.9	22.6	11.3	1.1	1.4	100

Table 6 and Table 7 present the wall type and roof type construction preferences in urban and rural areas. Presented data replicates that mud bonded brick/stone and cement-bonded brick/stone structures are the most common wall type. Similarly, GI sheet and concrete roofs are dominating roof types. With such conclusive facts, buildings in this study are chosen in such a way that these wall and roof types are included in the study. Figure 9 shows traditional roofing applied in residential buildings observed in Dhanusha and Udayapur districts of eastern Nepal.

a - Tile Roof (Dhanusha)

b - GI Sheet Roof (Udayapur)

c - Thatch Roof (Udayapur)

Figure 9: Traditional Roof Construction Practices in Various Part of Country

Case study buildings are identified based on climate variation, construction type variation and survey data. One building in each climate region (Subtropical, Temperate and Cold) is selected considering climate variation across country. Walls of buildings are of cement bonded brick type, mud bonded stone type and cement bonded stone type. Looking into the variety of roofing material, both concrete roofing and GI sheet roofing is included in case study buildings. Table 8 represents geographical and meteorological information about case study location of this research. Additionally, Figure 10 and Figure 11 represents constructional outlook of building at Dhanushadham and Hile respectively.

- Location 1: Dhanushadham Municipality-5, Nausay Bigha, Dhanusha
- Location 2: Pakribas Municipality-9, Hile, Dhankuta
- Location 3: Lomanthang Rural Municipality

Table 8: Details of case study building locations

Building Location	Coordinates	Altitude (m.a.s.l)	Yearly Lowest and Highest Temperature
Location 1	26.7°N, 85.9° E	82	5.9°C and 40.6°C
Location 2	26.9°N, 87.3° E	1948	-5.6°C and 29.4°C
Location 3	28.3°N, 84° E	4000	-15.2°C and 21.6°C

Figure 10: Case Study Building at Dhanushadham

Figure 11: Case Study Building at Hile

3.2 Survey and Field Study

Field study is taken as an important component of this research. Information gathered from field visits and site surveys have played a key role in the outcome of the research. The main intention of the survey is to have an idea about different construction practices and architectural designs in different parts of the country. Gathering knowledge about traditional building materials across different climate zones is one of the main motives for the survey. Outputs of the survey played major role in selection of case study buildings for the research.

A survey was conducted at 12 different locations in Nepal. They are as follow:

- Sindhuli Bazaar, Sindhuli
- Dhanushadham, Dhanusha
- Battar, Udayapur
- Betini, Udayapur
- Chhabise, Udayapur
- Dharan, Sunsari
- Hile, Dhankuta
- Myanglung, Terathum
- Jorpokhari, Panchthar
- Maipokhari, Ilam
- Fikkal, Ilam
- Birtamod, Jhapa

Detail study, questionnaire survey and measurements are also done at case study buildings. Building layout and its operational schedules are very crucial for energy performance modelling; hence they are determined through a survey. Apart from that, investigation of other local variables is also done at studied buildings.

Figure 12 shows constructional details of case study building at Hile being measured during field survey. Other important information extracted from the detail survey of case study buildings are:

- Building dimension, layout and orientation
- The material used in walls, roof, window, door and foundation of the building
- Occupants in a building
- Different schedules of building
- Internal heat gain of the building
- Thermal perception of residents residing in a building
- Passive techniques already existing in a building if any
- Indoor micro-climate measurement

Figure 12: Measurement of Buildings Constructional Properties

3.2.1 Monitoring Micro Climate of Case Study Buildings

Indoor temperature is essential for validating computer models of buildings. Buildings are monitored with standard data loggers. Standard calibrated HOBO MX and UX data loggers are used for data logging.

3.2.2 Building Airtightness Test

Building airtightness is a very important parameter to consider during building energy. Building airtightness gives us an idea about how leaky any building is. In other words, building airtightness is a measure of air leakage in or out of the building from surrounding when a building is in operation. Building airtightness tests are conducted at several locations in Nepal by N. Chaulagain 2020 [59]. Past results suggest that residential buildings in Nepal are not airtight and fail to meet the international standard. Measurements done at several locations followed by simulation have suggested that air leakage is very essential to measure and consider while performing building energy simulation.

Figure 13: Building Airtightness Test

Building airtightness test is done for this study to measure exact amount of air leakage (infiltration) of buildings. Figure 13 shows airtightness test arrangement which is carried out during field survey at Dharan, Sunsari. The airtightness test is performed using a calibrated standard Model 4 Minneapolis blower door test setup with DG-1000 pressure and flow gauge

with an accuracy of $\pm 0.4\%$ produced and distributed by The Energy Conservatory (TEC). Test is done following the guidelines given by technical standard ASTM E779. Potential investigation for leakage is also performed using a thermal imaging camera before performing a blower door test. Values are measured with automated experimental software and finally converted to ACH (Air Change per Hours) with dimensions of a building. Additionally, residents are also interviewed about their thermal comfort and other perceptions about their building environment. Figure 14 represents questionnaire survey being conducted to a resident at Myanglung, Terathum.

Figure 14: Questionnaire Survey of Resident at Myanglung Terathum

3.3 Selection of Alternative Materials

3.3.1 Autoclaved Aerated Concrete (AAC)

Autoclaved Aerated Concrete (AAC) is lightweight material mainly made of cement, fine aggregate and an expanding agent. AAC is widely used in Europe. It is gaining popularity in other parts of the globe for its lightweight, good thermal performance and structural strength. It has a good combination of workmanship along excellent thermal and mechanical properties. Apart from this, AAC displays good acoustic properties also [49],[62]-[63]. Manufacturing of AAC blocks involves blending several ingredients like cement, lime, water, fine aggregate and fly ash into a slurry. Once a slurry is made, an expansion agent is added to it. The final product will be obtained in block forms with good heat and sound insulating properties. The manufacturer claim that heating and cooling demand is roughly saved up to

20 percent as compared to traditional construction using AAC [64]. Figure 15 shows AAC being applied in a building.

Figure 15: AAC in Application [64]

Past researches done in AAC blocks has pointed out the benefits of using AAC as building wall material through their results. Shukla *et al.* 2015 have studied the thermal and energy performance of AAC and their result concludes that AAC has low conductivity as compared to bricks which are conventional building materials. The result further concludes that AAC performs well in terms of the energy demand of a building which is calculated utilizing simulation software in their study [65]. Kosny 1994 measured thermal and physical properties of commercially produced AAC blocks using the hot box measurement technique. After measurement of properties, thermal performance analysis is done with finite-difference computer modelling to evaluate the applicability of AAC in different cities of the USA. Results suggest that AAC can be used in various parts of the country with higher thermal efficiency [66]. These results can be related to several parts of Nepal where similar weather is expected. Table 9 compares physical and thermal properties identified by Sukla and Kosny.

Table 9: Comparisons between Thermal and Physical Properties of AAC Given by Sukla and Kosny

Author	Density (Kg/m ³)	Conductivity (W/mK)	Specific Heat Capacity (KJ/KgK)
Sukla <i>et al.</i>	450	0.114	0.84
Kosny	510.4	0.14	1.05

3.3.2 Phase Change Materials (PCM)

Phase change materials are used in buildings as Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems. PCMs are materials with very low melting temperature which falls within the range of building envelope operating temperature. When the temperature rises during the daytime and reaches the melting point of PCM, it absorbs latent heat. When the sun sets and temperature comes down, PCM releases latent heat while solidifying from the melted liquid. PCM simply stabilizes the room temperature. Different building elements can be constructed with PCM materials such as building walls, floors and ceiling. PCMs can be incorporated into these elements partially based on their applicability and effectiveness. Apart from these elements, PCMs can be used to make separate heat storage systems for a building [67], [68]. Figure 16 and Figure 17 shows classification and general working of PCM applied in a building.

Figure 16: Classification of PCM [68]

Figure 17: Working of PCMs in Building Application [69]

There are four different ways to apply PCM to construction materials. They are direct impregnation, immersion, shape stabilization and capsulation. The direct impregnation process involves mixing PCM directly into construction materials like cement, gypsum, etc. Immersion is dipping construction materials into liquid PCM. Construction materials like brick or wallboard absorb liquid PCM employing capillary action. The shape stabilization process is mixing PCM into supporting material. In this process, PCM is melted together with supporting material like high-density polyethylene. Then the melted mixture is cooled down to form a solid PCM with supporting material. The Capsulation process is enclosing PCM into a capsule-like shape formed by other materials. The Capsulation process is of 2 types: macro encapsulation and microencapsulation. If capsule size is very small ($1\mu\text{m} - 1000\mu\text{m}$) then the process is called microencapsulation. Macro encapsulation is generally bigger. The Capsulation process is attained by either a chemical or mechanical process [67], [68].

Dakhli *et al.* 2019 tested the effect of PCM added to the cement. Research studies thermal properties of PCM incorporated concrete. Sample composed of 0%, 10%, 20% and 30% PCM are tested in the study. Conductivity of pure concrete (0% PCM) is found as 0.7 W/mK. Similarly conductivity for 10%, 20% and 30% PCM containing sample are found to be 0.6 W/mK, 0.56 W/mK and 0.53 W/mK respectively [70]. Similar research is also done by Essid *et al.* 2020 by preparing concrete specimen containing 0%, 4.5%, 9% and 13% of PCM. Experimental measurements of these specimens notice a 15% increase in volumetric heat

storage of a 2cm thick concrete block with 15% PCM. The measured value was 3.13 MJ/m³K. Similarly, the thermal conductivity of concretes is found to be decreased by 30% with an addition of 13% PCM [71].

PCMs can be mixed with gypsum to prepare wallboard and cement boards to stabilize indoor temperature. Borreguero *et al.* 2014 prepared a sample of gypsum boards incorporated with stabilized PCM and tested its thermal and physical properties. Their result shows that physical and thermal properties are within the European standard requirements while saving energy up to 10.20 KWh/m³ [72]. Mandilaras *et al.* 2013 monitored the 2 story building which is constructed with a gypsum board containing PCM. Monitoring results show that the average indoor temperature of a building did not go beyond 30°C and fall below 15°C throughout the year during the measurement period in the Mediterranean climate of Greece [73].

3.3.3 Cross Laminated Timber (CLT)

Cross Laminated Timber is also known as CLT is timber-based construction material mostly used in cold climates of Europe. In recent times, CLT is gaining popularity in different parts of North America, especially in the USA and Canada. A major advantage of CLT is that it has very good thermal performance. Additionally, CLT brings an excellent opportunity to offsite manufacturing which reduces construction cost [74]. Some standout advantages of CLT are:

- Low carbon footprint during production
- Excellent airtightness
- Good load distribution
- Light weight
- Fast onsite construction
- Good finishing
- Reduces labor cost

CLT normally consists of 3-7 layers of lumber boards stacked crosswise (in 90 degrees). Lumber is normally made of spruce or pine and is glued together in an odd number of layers. 3 layered CLT is used for light construction such as non-load bearing walls. If walls are load-bearing then 5 layered CLT is used. 7 layered CLT is used for floor and other heavy construction purposes. Layers in the CLT panel are designed based on load requirement

hence they can be more than 7 also. The thickness of individual lumber pieces may vary from 16 mm to 51 mm and the width may vary from about 60 mm to 240 mm [75], [76].

Sutton *et al.* 2011 have presented the conductivity and density of CLT in their article. Thermal conductivity is measured as 0.13 W/mK and density is 480-500 Kg/m³ for spruce [74]. Tripathi and Rice 2017 conducted various measurements of laminated strand lumber (LSL) and red spruce. Thermal conductivity is measured as 0.09 W/mK - 0.012 W/mK. Similarly, density is found as 680Kg/m³ for LSL and 460 Kg/m³ for red spruce. Research also concludes that conductivity variation is very low with variation in moisture content [77]. Figure 18 shows 5 layered CLT combined with insulating material used in a building wall. Similarly, Figure 19 shows application of CLT panel in a building seen in cold climates of Tallinn, Estonia.

Figure 18: Different Layers of Lumber Boards in CLT

CLTs are commercially available in the international market. SKONTO ENTERPRISES is a similar organization providing CLT with different dimensions and designs. Its product has a high heat storage capacity (1300 J/kgK) as compared to concrete (880 J/kgK). Thermal conductivity: 0.13 W/mK. [78] Other properties are mentioned below.

- Density: 480–500 kg/m³

Compressive strength:

- 2.5 N/mm² (perpendicular to the grain of boards)
- 21 N/mm² (parallel to the grain of boards)

Bending strength:

- 24 N/mm² (parallel to the grain of boards)

Elastic modulus:

- 370 N/mm² (perpendicular to the grain of boards)
- 11,500 N/mm² (parallel to the grain of boards)

Figure 19: CLT in Application

3.3.4 Improved Brick

Brick is one of the widely used building envelope materials across the globe. In Nepalese building construction practice also, brick is taken as a go-to material for modern buildings. It is easily available in Nepalese market as compared to other materials. The recent quest for

the improvement of building materials has led to changes in brick and concrete blocks. The main aim is to increase the thermal resistivity of construction material by adding substitutional materials. While doing so, waste products of the industrial and agricultural sector are mainly considered as an appropriate additive in brick with sustainability and economical aspect. Many research shows the effects of the addition of materials like straw, saw dust, paper wastes, rice husk and polyurethane. Results indicate that these materials can be efficiently added to brick and concrete blocks to enhance thermal resistivity without compromising on their mechanical strengths [79]–[83].

Sindanne *et al.* 2014 mixed cement and lime as stabilizers in earth blocks which are used for building construction. Results show that these stabilizers increase mechanical properties. However, these additives do not enhance thermal properties. To overcome this issue, they added saw dust in different ratios to earth block and noted the change in thermal properties. The conductivity of a block with 12% of saw dust mixture is measured and found to be reduced by 8.47% from its original value [79]. Madrid *et al.* 2018 prepared a sample of a dry unit with 5% of sawdust and 15% of lime mud substitution in their research. Upon testing, the addition of sawdust is found to be reducing the thermal conductivity of CMU. On the other hand, reduction of compressive strength by addition of sawdust is compensated by added lime mud. Sample with 5% sawdust measures to have 18.5% more thermal resistance compared to reference CMU. Similarly, a sample with 5% sawdust and 15% lime mud added shows an increase in thermal resistance by 11.1% [80].

Beal *et al.* 2019 developed clay bricks with different pore-forming additives. Three pore-forming additives (also known as filler) are vermiculite, wood ash and sawdust. The filler to clay ratio of these samples is taken as 20%, 25% and 15 % by weight, respectively for vermiculite, wood ash and sawdust. Result suggests that vermiculite and sawdust addition into brick results in a decrease in thermal conductivity by 20% and 37% each as conductivity values are measured as 0.24 W/mK and 0.16 W/mK respectively [81]. A similar method of creating pores inside brick is developed by Shibib *et al.* 2013 and noticed in the reduction of conductivity of brick. They added saw dust in clay while preparing brick and when the brick entered the oven, saw dust burned leaving pores inside the brick. Results indicates decrease in conductivity from 0.9 to 0.46 W/mK [82]. Banhidi *et al.* 2008 developed methods of improving the thermal properties of brick and evaluated the results in their research. Three different additives in the form of sawdust, rice husk and seed shell are used. Measurement results demonstrate that the addition of sunflower seed shells is most effective among all other additives. The addition of this shell by 7% of weight results decrease in thermal

conductivity of brick from 0.27 W/mK to 0.17 W/mK [83]. Figure 20 shows different types of improved brick.

Figure 20: Different Types of Brick (pure clay, vermiculate, wood ash and sawdust from left to right) [81]

3.3.5 Drywall

Gypsum board is popular building envelope material which is also known as drywall. These boards are easy to manufacture and install at a construction site. Mass manufacturing is also possible as offsite construction which reduces construction time and cost. These boards are light and are often used as internal partition and ceiling material. Cement board is similar to drywall but it performs better with moist environment hence can be used as outer wall materials also. Cement boards are also made of gypsum but it comprised of cement mortar. Cement boards are generally heavy and hard because of the presence of cement. Gypsum boards are of two types; Type 'X' and Type 'C'. Type 'X' is fire resistant board with fire resistance up to 1 hour. Type 'C' is also fire resistant board with 2-4 hours of fire resistance abilities with the following properties[84], [85].

- Specific heat capacity: 1089 J/KgK
- Thermal conductivity: 0.258 W/mK
- Density: 752 Kg/m³

Fiber Cement board is also a type of cement board with reinforced fiber present in it. Cement board can already be used as outdoor wall material. Additional presence of fibers in it makes it more strong and suitable for a building envelope material. These are normally heavy boards with fire-resistant properties. Following are some important properties of cement board [86], [87]:

- Specific heat capacity: 600 J/KgK
- Thermal conductivity: less than 0.12 W/mK
- Density: 1.3 -1.4 g/cm³

3.3.6 Specifications of Studied Materials

Based on a literature review of materials, the following materials are found to be best suited to be used as NBM with potential thermal performance enhancements of NRBs. Most of the materials are used as a wall material in this study except for PCM concrete which is used as ceiling material. Table 10 presents comparison of thermal properties of all materials which are considered as NBM in this research.

Table 10: Specification of NBM

Description	Material	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Density (Kg/m ³)	Specific Heat capacity (KJ/KgK)	Reference
Wall1	AAC	0.14	510.4	1.05	Kosny [66]
Wall2	PCM Drywall	0.261	1126.17	2.38	Borreguero et al. [72]
Wall3	CLT	0.13	500	1.3	SKONTO ENTERPRIS ES [78]
Wall4	Sawdust Brick	0.19	839	0.8	Beal et al [81]
Wall5	Fiber Cement board + Type C Gypsum board	0.12 and 0.258	1400 and 752	0.6 and 0.752	Park <i>et al.</i> , Vasco and LONRACE [84]–[87]
Ceiling	PCM Concrete	2.01	2184	1.43	Essid et al. [71]

3.4 TRNSYS Simulation

Building energy performance simulation is done with help of TRNSYS18 software. Weather data is also required to perform simulation in TRNSYS. Real weather data is not available for

the studied locations of this study. Meteornorm software is used to generate interpolated data files. Both software is available at Energy Lab, Kathmandu University, Dhulikhel.

Typical building simulation in TRNSYS requires a separate building modelling in TRNBuild. While working with TRNBuild, architectural details of each thermal zone within the building need to be presented. Parameters like zone volume, orientation, wall material, area and thickness are included while modelling each building. Additionally, occupancy details and internal heat gain sources are also required to be incorporated in the building model. All these data are studied during site visits and surveys conducted to building occupants. Once the building modelling is done at TRNBuild, the model is simulated at TRNSYS Studio which is a graphical simulation platform of the TRNSYS package. Figure 21 represents overall modelling of a building in TRNBuild and Simulation Studio.

Figure 21: TRNSYS Simulation Approach for Multi-zone Building

Once the modelling and simulation of the buildings are done output is obtained in two forms. The first form of the output is the indoor temperature of each zone. These temperatures can be calculated for every hour throughout the year assuming that there are no auxiliary heating and cooling arrangement in the zones. Zone temperature is calculated in the existing condition of every studied building. The main purpose of this result is for the validation and

calibration of building models. Temperature calculated is compared with monitored data and past research to validate the models. Figure 22 presents overall modelling approach of a building in TRNSYS.

Figure 22: Workflow in TRNSYS

Once the model is calibrated then each building is modeled by replacing existing building material with NBMs. Again buildings with NBMs are simulated. Output result is then taken in the form of heating and cooling load. To get heating and cooling demand, external heating and cooling arrangement need to be installed in a building. This is carried out by setting the heating setpoint as 18°C and cooling set point as 24°C in building models with NBMs. Heating and cooling schedules are according to occupancy in the zone.

3.4.1 Condition Setup for Simulation

Some conditions are set up while performing building energy modelling and simulation. These parameters and conditions influence the outcome of the simulation. These are:

- The heating set point is 18°C and the cooling set point is 24°C
- Sky View Factor (SVF) is 0.5 for vertical walls and 1 for ceiling
- While calculating internal gains, ISO 7730 is selected
- Lighting gain is taken as 2.5 W/m²

Some conditions are set up while performing TRNSYS simulation-based on-site surveys and questionnaires to the occupants. They are as follow:

- Architectural details of building such as orientation, dimension and material selection
- Number of occupants and hour of occupancy
- sources of heat gain such as light bulb, fridge, refrigerator and their hour of operation
- Activity of occupants

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter includes the results and key findings of the research. The existing condition of all three case study buildings is explained in this section. Results are presented in two terms; hourly indoor temperature of zones in a building and thermal (heating and cooling) demand. Heating and cooling demand are calculated based on heat setpoint and cooling setpoint in each thermal zone. For this research, the heating setpoint and cooling setpoint are defined as 18°C and 24°C, respectively. Heating and cooling arrangement is assumed to be turned off when there is no occupancy at a particular zone through schedules in the simulation studio. The schedule is prepared based on the resident's response during the survey. Once results are calculated for existing conditions, similar results are calculated for other materials (NBM). Results of NBM are compared with the results of an existing condition. Building performance with the intervention of passive techniques like infiltration and thermal mass is also presented in this section.

4.1 Building Thermal Performance Study

4.1.1 Dhanushadham (B1)

The study location Dhanushadham is located at Dhanusha district in southern Nepal with coordinates of 26.7° N latitude and 85.9° E longitude. The study building is located at an altitude of 82 m.a.s.l with a semi-urban human settlement. Dhanushadham is a warm and temperate climate with an average outdoor temperature of 24.9°C. Summer is normally hot and winter is cool with Minimum and maximum outdoor temperatures as 5.9°C and 40.6°C respectively. Figure 23 shows the outdoor temperature at the study location throughout the year.

Figure 23: Outdoor Temperature at Dhanushadham

Building Details

The building which is selected for study is a single-story building with 2 rooms in it. The building wall is constructed with cement bonded bricks with cement plaster on both sides of it. Wall thickness is 0.177 m including 0.025 m thick plaster on both sides. The roof of the building is of concrete with a thickness of 0.127m. Details of building components are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Constructional Details of Building B1

Building Component	Material	Thickness
Wall	Cement bonded brick with cement plaster on both sides	0.177m and 0.025 plaster
Roof	GI sheet	1 mm
Window	Pine wood	0.0381 m
Door	Pine wood	0.0381 m
Floor	Concrete	0.15m

4.1.1.1 Initial Building Performance

The year-round temperature of both zone 1 and zone 2 is calculated and divided into three categories. The first category is defined as heating degree hours where hourly temperatures which are below 18°C are counted. The second category is the comfort range where temperatures vary between 18°C and 24°C. The third one is cooling degree hours with temperatures more than 24°C.

a : Yearly temperature of Zone-1 and Zone-2 *b* : Classification of Yearly indoor temperature

Figure 24: Hourly Temperature Distribution of B1 at Existing Condition

Figure 24 illustrates year-round hourly temperatures in percentage. Figure a encapsulates year-round hourly temperature of both thermal zones. Similarly, Figure b shows classification of hourly temperatures into three different groups explained earlier. It is observed that both zones have identical temperature distribution. Temperature measures as much as 42°C during summer. The least indoor temperature is calculated as 8.7°C during winter. The result shows that comfort hour is only 20% of total hours throughout the year. The remaining hours are either heating degree hours or cooling degree hours. Just more than 10% of data are heating degree hours whereas cooling degree hour accounts for almost 70% of a year. Hence it is clear that the study location is a cooling dominant place.

Alternative method of evaluating indoor thermal comfort is a calculation of the heating and cooling demand of the building. Cooling demand is calculated as 4924.19 KW in the existing condition. In contrast, heating demand is only 386.4 KW. Annual energy demand for heating and cooling is shown in Figure 25. Figure shows cumulative energy demand for 12 months of service for building B1 along with monthly demand for every month. It can be observed that cooling demand is at a peak during the summer months resulting in a sharp rise in the total energy demand of a building. In contrast, heating demand is minimal only during winter (December-February). Hence study location is cooling dominant case.

Figure 25: Heating and Cooling Demand of B1 at Existing Condition

4.1.1.2 Building Performance with NBMs

This section contains the building performance of Dhanushadham building B1, constructed with selected NBMs. Annual energy demand is calculated and compared with an existing condition. Performance with different values of thermal mass and infiltration is calculated and the best performing case is identified. Building is modelled with all NBMs including PCM ceiling. B1 is the only building which is studied with implementation of PCM ceiling because it has concrete roof in existing condition; hence it is possible to replace it directly with PCM ceiling.

Table 12: Reduction in Annual Energy Demand of B1 with different thickness of PCM Ceiling

Ceiling thickness (m)	Reduction in Annual Energy Demand		
	Heating demand (%)	Cooling demand (%)	Total demand (%)
0.1	-2.51	-1.79	-1.84
0.23	12.5	4.8	5.36
0.35	18.95	5.17	6.17

Table 12 shows a reduction in the annual energy demand of a building with different thicknesses of PCM ceiling. Energy demand seems to be increasing instead of decrease at thickness of 0.1 m. This is because this thickness of ceiling is too thin to act as a thermal barrier. The result indicates that further increase in thickness reduces higher percentage of annual energy demand.

Unlike PCM ceiling, AAC construction seems to have a negative effect by thermal mass. Table 13 presents a reduction in the annual energy demand of a building designed with AAC. The results indicate that 0.22 m thickness of AAC as envelope material has the best performance as compared to thicker walls. Further increase of wall thickness from 0.22 m increases thermal mass and traps the higher amount of heat inside a building which increases cooling load.

Table 13: Reduction in Annual Energy Demand of B1 with Different Thickness of AAC

Wall thickness (m)	Reduction in Annual Energy Demand		
	Heating demand (%)	Cooling demand (%)	Total demand (%)
0.22	27.46	11.56	12.72
0.30	30.89	11.0	12.45
0.356	31.32	10.83	12.32
0.45	32.30	10.25	11.86

Results suggest that proper application of PCM drywall is also beneficial in a climate like Dhanushadham. Wall thickness should be selected carefully in the case of PCM drywall to get the maximum benefit from it. Neither very thin nor very thick walls seem to be beneficial with this material. Figure 25 shows a reduction in yearly energy demand with different thicknesses of PCM drywall applied in building B1. Too thin wall may act as a counterproductive technique in an attempt to decrease energy demand. 0.038 m thick wall of PCM drywall is modelled with building B1. Result suggests that annual thermal load increases with this design. As wall thickness increases, energy demand gradually decreases. Result shows that applying too thick wall is also not so effective in this design. Load reduction percentage sharply rises up to thickness of 0.152m as shown in figure 25. Further increase in thermal mass is less effective. This is because at 0.15 m thickness, wall is already

acting at optimum thermal barrier. Similar results can be observed with design with CLT as a wall material. Gradual increment of wall thickness upto 0.2 meters results depletion in annual thermal load as much as 12.44%. Further increase in thickness is not beneficial because thermal mass has already reached at utmost level. Table 14 exhibits studied wall thicknesses of CLT at building B1 and their annual thermal load reduction.

Figure 26: Annual Thermal Load reduction with Different Thermal Mass of PCM Drywall

Table 14: Reduction in Annual Energy Demand of B1 with Different Thickness of CLT

Wall thickness (m)	Reduction in Annual Energy Demand		
	Heating demand (%)	Cooling demand (%)	Total demand (%)
0.045	-10.8	-7.49	-7.73
0.1	7.07	7.64	7.6
0.2	28.1	11.21	12.44
0.25	30.85	10.74	12.21

Another envelope material that is integrated at building B1 as a passive technique is sawdust brick. Sawdust brick also possesses a high potential to reduce the annual thermal load of building B1. Sawdust wall thickness to 0.45 m shows decrease in annual thermal load by only 11.14 % which is even lesser than 0.23 m wall. Among all designed thicknesses, 0.23 m wall resulted highest thermal load reduction which is 11.51%. Further increase in wall thickness seems to be reducing heating load but increases cooling demand because of excessive heat trapping resulted by high thermal mass. This out-turn decline in overall thermal load because the building is cooling dominant one.

Gypsum Board (GB) and Cement Board (CB) are combined to form a wall that has the potential to reduce annual energy demand in a subtropical climate like Dhanushadham. Gypsum board and cement board are ordinarily manufactured with thinner dimensions. Hence this study also considered initial design with 0.035 m thickness of wall combined with GB and CB and increased thickness based on material availability. Four designs of building B1 are studied with panel thickness of 0.035 m, 0.07 m, 0.14 m and 0.25 m. These designs ensue the reduction in year round energy demand by -22.07%, -7.28%, 7.2% and 11.39% respectively. Results suggest that thicker boards perform better as compared to thinner boards in terms of both heating and cooling aspect.

This research considers infiltration as one of the passive design technique to improve building thermal performance. Building B1 is also designed with different infiltration rates integrated with NBM. Best performing wall thickness is considered for every material from previous result while examining infiltration effect. Infiltration value varies between 1 ACH to 10 ACH for every material construction in this research. Results of infiltration variation are almost identical for all NBM design. Every NBM designed with 1 ACH infiltration value consumes least energy for achieving thermal comfort. Outdoor temperature is hot during summer surpassing comfort range. In such scenario, minimal quantity of air exchange between building and surrounding effects to lower indoor temperature. Hence, NBM design associated with lower infiltration value is recommended for their application on building B1. Annual energy demand of B1 with NBMs at 1 ACH infiltration is presented in Figure 27. It is possible to reduce the annual energy demand up-to 3351.07 KW from existing demand of 5310.59 KW by designing building envelopes with NBMs.

Figure 27: Comparison of Yearly Thermal Load of NBMs at B1

4.1.2 Hile (B2)

This section contains the detailed result of thermal performance analysis of building B2 which is located at Hile. Case study location Hile is located at Dhankuta District of eastern Nepal with coordinates of 26.9° north latitude and 87.3° East longitude. It is a hilly region with an elevation of 1948 m.a.s.l. It comes under a temperate climate zone. The lowest outdoor temperature is -5.6°C and the highest is 29.4°C with an average temperature of 15.06°C. Figure 28 represents the yearly temperature variation of Hile.

Figure 28: Ambient Temperature of Hile

Building Details

The study building at Hile is a cement-bonded stone masonry type building. The building is constructed with a traditional design with GI sheet roofing. The building includes 3 thermal zones which are mainly used as kitchen, bedroom and store-room. The roof of a bedroom is insulated with wooden planks of 0.0381 m thickness. The building is occupied by 2 occupants during the daytime and 3 during the night. Through field survey, it is found that occupants tend to spend most of the time in the kitchen during the daytime. The bedroom is occupied mostly during night time only. Table 15 exhibits constructional specifications of the building B2.

Table 15: Constructional Details of Building B2

Building Component	Material	Thickness
Wall	Cement bonded stone with mud mortar on both sides	0.508 m
Roof	GI sheet	1 mm
Window	Wood	0.0381 m
Door	Wood	0.0381 m
Floor	Earthen	

4.1.2.1 Existing Building Performance

Zone 3 which is generally used as a storeroom remains unoccupied most of the time. Hence comfort condition is not necessary for the zone. This zone is omitted for analysis and annual energy demand load calculation. Zone 1 (kitchen) and Zone 2 (bedroom) are considered for further study.

a: Yearly Indoor Temperature variation b: Grouping of Yearly Indoor Temperature

Figure 29: Indoor Temperature Distribution of Building B2 at Existing Condition

Figure 29 represents the yearly distribution of indoor temperature of zone 1 and zone 2 of building B2. Figure a presents comparison of kitchen and bedroom year round temperatures and suggests that the temperature of both zones is identical. There is no difference in the annual energy demand of both zones because of their identical thermal condition. Figure b illustrates that temperature below 18 °C is more than 50 % of total hours in both rooms. Total comfort hours (18°C-24°C) counts as 3294 hours for zone 1 and 3367 for zone 2 which is a little less than 40% of total hours in a year.

Figure 30: Annual Energy Demand of Building B2 at Existing Condition

Figure 30 shows the annual energy demand of building B1 in the existing condition. The graph illustrates that energy demand is largely contributed by heating demand alone. There is barely any cooling demand in the building except in the months of June-Aug. During that period, heating demand is very low. The major energy-consuming period of the year is winter (Nov-Mar). Out of a total of 10877.71 KW of annual energy demand, the heating load is 10516.58 KW and the cooling load is only 361.12 KW. Result also concludes that building indoor environment is within comfort range for almost half year because there is very less energy demand during monsoon and post-monsoon season.

4.1.2.2 Building Performance with NBMs

Building B2 is modelled with selected five envelop materials one by one to evaluate thermal performance. PCM ceiling is not implemented in B2 because like to like replacement is not possible considering the fact that existing roof is of GI sheet. Different wall thickness are implemented for every material during first phase of analysis to estimate effect of thermal mass.

AAC has good potential to reduce the annual energy demand of a building. Results suggest that AAC construction is sensitive to thermal mass. An increase in wall thickness increases the percentage of yearly energy demand reduction. However, building performance saturates after reaching optimum thermal mass level. Initial thickness examined by this research is 0.2 m which resulted in reduction of building thermal load by almost 18%. Further 0.1 m increase of CLT thickness resulted in thermal load reduction by more than 19%. Increase in thickness beyond 0.3 m show very less improvement as the wall has already achieved optimal level of thermal barrier. Table 16 shows the overall thermal performance of AAC on building B2.

Table 16: Annual Energy Demand of Building B2 with Different Thickness of AAC

Wall thickness (m)	Annual energy demand		
	Heating demand (KW)	Cooling demand (KW)	Total reduction (%)
0.2	8583.24	341.41	17.95
0.3	8460.9	326.9	19.21
0.35	8435.3	330.41	19.41
0.45	8406.7	330.4	19.67

Hile is heating dominant region and low thermal mass cannot provide sufficient thermal barrier to the indoor environment. Hence, relatively thinner walls increase energy demand instead of decreasing. Higher thermal mass decreases overall thermal load of a building. However, after optimum wall thickness thermal performance of a material saturates and further energy demand capacity of a material is very less. Figure 31, Figure 32, Figure 33 and Figure 34 show existing energy demand reduction capacities of CLT, PCM Drywall, Sawdust Brick and GB & CB wall employed at B2. Every material construction shows similar effect with different variation of thermal mass. Results show that almost 20% of existing energy demand reduction is possible with 0.45 m wall of AAC construction accounting for which is highest among all studied thicknesses of NBMs.

Figure 31: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B2 with CLT

Figure 32: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B2 with PCM Drywall

Figure 33: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B2 with Sawdust Brick

Figure 34: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B2 with GB and CB

Cooling demand reduction is negative in case of all materials. Building B2 is performing better at existing condition as compared to NBMs. All NBMs applied at B2 are with higher thermal resistivity which can provide maximum thermal barrier to indoor building environment. Higher thermal barrier results more heat trap inside building during summer which in turn increases cooling load. However, cooling load is very less as compared to heating load (3.31 % of total load) at existing condition. Hence all NBMs have potential to reduce overall annual existing thermal energy demand of a building despite increasing the cooling load.

Infiltration is also key aspect of passive design technique. Performance of NBMs can be improved with leak-proof construction. Constructional design of every material is simulated under various infiltration levels. Every design is evaluated from 1 ACH level to 9 ACH level of air exchange rate. Similar results are observed for every design. Infiltration rate should be as less as possible for better thermal performance. Result show that maximum possible annual load reduction is at 1 ACH infiltration rate for all material construction variation. Figure 35 illustrates the comparison of year-round thermal energy demand of building B2 at existing condition and other material construction at 1 ACH infiltration. Figure shows that AAC construction is least energy demanding among all other design variations which is 88.31% lesser than existing demand (10877.71 KW). Building construction of PCM Drywall, CLT, Sawdust Brick and GB and CB also reduce existing demand with annual energy demand of just more than 2000 KW.

Figure 35: Comparison of Yearly Thermal Load of NBMs at B2

4.1.3 Lomanthang (B3)

The third case study building is located at Lomanthang Rural Municipality in Mustang District of Nepal. The study location is located at an altitude of 4000 m.a.s.l with coordinates of 28.3° north and 84° east. The climate of Lomanthang comes under the cold category with yearly minimum and maximum temperatures as -15.2°C and 21.6°C respectively. The average temperature at Lomanthang measures 5.8°C. Figure 36 shows the annual hourly temperature distribution of Lomanthang.

Figure 36: Yearly Ambient Temperature of Lomanthang

Case study building (B3) is a single-story building of mud bonded stone type building with GI sheet roofing. The roof and floor are insulated with wood planks from inside. Walls in all directions are also insulated up to 3 feet from inside using wood. The building is owned by Nepal Army with 30 occupants almost throughout a year. The window and door both are made of timber. The building consists of only one thermal zone with an attic above it. Two bathrooms are attached to the building from the northeast and southwest side. Table 17 presents constructional details of building B3. Building is mainly constructed with stone and wood. Stone is used to provide structural envelop whereas wood is used for insulation. Similarly Figure 37 shows architectural design of B3 from front.

Table 17: Constructional Details of Building B3

Building Component	Material	Thickness
Wall	Mud bonded stone with wooden parquetting up-to 3 feet from floor	0.457 m
Roof	Plywood ceiling with GI sheet roofing	12 mm + 1 mm
Window	Wood	0.0381 m
Door	Wood	0.0381 m
Floor	Earthen with wooden parquetting	

Figure 37: Front Elevation of Building B3

4.1.3.1 Existing Building Performance

The ambient temperature never goes above 24°C in a year at the study location. Simulation result and outdoor temperature profile conclude that B3 is heating dominant building. Hourly indoor temperature distribution suggests that more than 98% of temperature readings are below 18°C which results in a huge heating load in a building. Occupants are present in a building for most of the time of a day throughout the year suggesting that heating is needed for a whole year.

Figure 38: Hourly Temperature Distribution of Building B3 at Existing Condition

Table 18: Temperature Range of Building B3 at Existing Condition

Temperature Range	Total Hours	Percentage
<18°C	8359	95.5 %
18°C to 24°C	401	4.5 %
>24	0	0 %

Figure 38 represents yearly indoor temperatures calculated from the TRNSYS model. The result shows that indoor temperature never goes beyond the 24°C temperature. Hence there are not any cooling hours. However, more than 95% of indoor temperatures are found to be lesser than 18°C in hourly scale. Table 18 shows the total number of hours in a year falling in the different temperature ranges. It indicates that only 4.5 % of hours in a year fall within the comfort range i.e. 18°C-24°C. To maintain a building at a thermally comfortable indoor temperature 267.96 MW of energy is required at the existing condition. Total energy demand rises sharply during winter (Oct-Mar) as shown in figure 39. Energy demand is lesser during summer as compared to winter because of relatively hotter days in summer.

Figure 39: Annual Thermal Load of Building B3 at Existing Condition

4.1.3.2 Building Performance with NBMs

Building B3 is designed with different thicknesses of NBMs to evaluate their performance based on thermal mass variation. Building envelope is changed with all NBMs one after another considering thermal mass variation for all of them. AAC possesses good potential to reduce yearly thermal load. Two design variations in terms of thermal mass of AAC are considered (layer thickness of 0.356 m and 0.45 m). Yearly energy demand reduction is calculated as 4.03% and 4.26% respectively for 0.356 m and 0.45 m construction respectively. Further increase in thermal mass is not considered as performance is already at saturated level.

Another design change made at B3 by this research is implementing PCM drywall as wall envelope material. Reduction of existing energy demand by different layer thickness is studied. Similar effect is observed with implementation of CLT into B3 as a wall material. Both CLT and PCM Drywall have negative effect in terms of thermal performance with comparatively thinner wall thickness. As thickness increases, their thermal performance also increases. After reaching optimum thickness level, their performance also saturates. Figure 40 and Figure 41 represent annual existing energy demand reduction by PCM Drywall and CLT respectively integrated at B3. Results show that potential load reduction raises sharply up-to thickness of around 0.3 m. Further increase in wall thickness is not useful beyond this as wall has already attained optimum thermal resistivity level. In case CLT application, wall thickness of 0.35 m resulted in weaker performance as compared to 0.3 m thick wall. This

phenomenon occurs when thermal mass of the wall is too high so that the building cannot get benefits of solar heat gain. Indoor temperature cannot increase because of heavy thermal barrier despite having warmer outdoor temperature during daytime. As a result of this, heating load increase leading to increment in overall energy demand.

Figure 40: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B3 with PCM Drywall

Figure 41: Annual Energy Demand Reduction of B3 with CLT

Building b3 is modeled with sawdust to see potential energy demand reduction strategies. Initial design thickness of sawdust brick wall implemented at B3 is selected as 0.356 m and immediate improvement in thermal performance is noticed through simulation. Buildings with thicker layers are designed next and simulated. Their thermal performances are shown in table 19. Results presented in the table show that thermal performance increases with an increase in the thermal mass of the brick wall. Further increase in energy demand reduction potential become very less after certain thickness of brick applied to the wall. Results show that increment of layer thickness by 0.1 m from 0.4 m results increase in energy demand reduction potential by just 0.24%.

Table 19: Annual Energy Demand of Building B3 with Different Thickness of Sawdust Brick

Wall thickness (m)	Annual energy demand		
	Heating demand (MW)	Cooling demand (MW)	Total reduction (%)
0.356	258.070	0	3.69
0.4	252.410	0	5.8
0.45	252.052	0	5.93
0.5	251.764	0	6.04

Integration of different layer thicknesses of GB and CB is carried out in building B3. Thermal performances of these designs are evaluated in terms of existing annual energy demand reduction potential through computer modelling. Comparatively thinner layers of materials applied at envelope produces less effect. In contrast, design with thicker wall have higher tendency to reduce existing thermal load. Table 20 presents thermal performances of all designed layers of GB and CB integrated at B3. Results show that 0.178 m layers of each GB and CB have tendency to reduce yearly energy by 3.9% which is less than thinner layer combining of both GB and CB (0.2 m and 0.075 m). Hence layer of GB should be higher compared to CB for better performance.

Table 20: Annual Energy Demand of Building B3 with Different Thickness of GB and CB

Wall thickness (m) [GB+ CB]	Annual energy demand		
	Heating demand (KW)	Cooling demand (KW)	Total reduction (%)
0.038 + 0.005	277261.21	0	-3.47
0.1 + 0.01	263440.11	0	1.69
0.2 + 0.075	254749.02	0	4.93
0.178 + 0.178	257523.82	0	3.9
0.3 + 0.1	253218.56	0	5.5

Another passive technique intervention considered by this research at B3 is infiltration. After evaluation of thermal performances of different thicknesses of NBMs, best performing layer thickness of each material is selected for further analysis of infiltration. For each NBM, 9 different variations of infiltration values (1 ACH to 9 ACH) are designed and thermal performances are evaluated. Results show that every NBM construction designed at B3 performs better with lower infiltration rate. Annual energy demand increases with an increase in air exchange rate between building and surrounding. Figure 42 demonstrates comparison of existing building thermal performance with building design variations with NBMs at 1 ACH infiltration rate. Results show that annual energy demand can be reduced by more than 80% with proper selection of material and airtight construction. Yearly thermal load of all materials selected for study is around 50 MW when designed with 1 ACH air exchange rate given that existing load is 267.96 MW.

Figure 42: Comparison of Yearly Thermal Load of NBMs at B3

Table 21 represents the percentage reduction of existing yearly energy demand by new materials at optimized conditions (best thickness and infiltration) for all three buildings.

Table 21: Existing Load Reduction Percentage of Buildings by Different Materials Optimized with Thermal Mass and Infiltration

Building	Annual Energy Demand Reduction With Optimized Passive Interventions (%)					
	AAC	PCM Drywall	CLT	Sawdust Brick	GB and CB	PCM Ceiling
B1	36.89	29.75	36.52	35.39	35.25	29.18
B2	88.32	76.37	77.64	78.15	77.72	
B3	81.19	81.61	80.92	81.38	80.97	

4.2 Validation

TRNSYS simulation result depends on simulation models prepared. Results of this research are generated in two forms; indoor temperature and thermal load. The accuracy of the initial building model determines the reliability of the final results. Hence all building models in existing conditions are validated first by means of indoor temperature of a zone.

Temperatures are validated by comparing the simulated data with real-time measured temperatures. Once the model is validated in all three case study locations, the same model is considered as a base model for further analysis.

ASHRAE guideline explains the process of determining reliability of building model for simulation. Guideline provides methods to perform uncertainty analysis between calculated indoor temperature through simulation and measured temperatures values. This research has considered two uncertainty indices namely NMBE and CV(RMSE). NMBE (Normalized Mean Biased Error) is helpful in determining whether the calculated values are under predicted or over predicted. It is calculated using following formula. NMBE is recommended to be analyzed along with any other parameter as the negative and positive errors tend to cancel out each other in this parameter[88].

$$\text{NMBE} = \frac{1}{m} \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (m_i - s_i)}{n - p} \times 100 (\%)$$

CV(RMSE) (Coefficient of Variation of the Root Mean Square Error) is considered for model reliability test to supplement the simulation model of the research given by following equation.

$$\text{CV(RMSE)} = \frac{1}{m} \times \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (m_i - s_i)^2}{n - p}} \times 100 (\%)$$

Measured and simulated temperatures of a thermal zone are represented in the equation by m_i and s_i respectively. Total number of measured values is indicated by n and mean of these values is represented by m in the equation. Value of p is suggested as zero for calibration purpose.

The B3 building model is validated using previous research done by Rijal 2021 [23]. Research presents measurements of indoor temperature values during winter season. The indoor temperature generated by the B3 building model is in close agreement with measurements presented in previous research. Daily mean difference between indoor and outdoor temperature is experimentally measured as 2.8°C. Whereas the difference is 2.27°C for simulated data. Similarly, the B2 building model is also validated with results presented in previous research done by Gautam et al 2019 [17]. Average simulated daytime temperature of building B2 is 14.1 °C in the month of December which is consistent with published data presented in the paper. Hence conclusion can be drawn as simulated temperature at both

buildings closely matches with experimentally measured ones. Existing building models are reliable enough for further analysis and their simulation results are definitive.

Building B1 model is validated with real temperature measurement of zone 2 of the building. Indoor temperature is measured using a data logger from Jan 1- Feb 15, 2021. These measurements are compared with simulated temperature using NMBE and CV(RMSE) values. These parameters are calculated using above mentioned formula. ASHRAE guideline mentions that permissible values for NMBE and CV(RMSE) are ± 10 and 30 respectively for hourly calculation. The value of NMBE is calculated as -4.7 and CV(RMSE) as 25.22 for this research. These calculations validate that the factors are within the permissible limit of the ASHRAE guideline [88]. Hence the existing building model is reliable and its output is dependable for any conclusion drawn afterwards.

Figure 43: Measured vs Calculated Temperature of Building B1.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The main intention of this study is to identify new materials with the potential to reduce the annual thermal load of Nepalese residential buildings and to evaluate their performances. Total 6 materials that are considered to be better performing and gaining popularity in the international building construction market are identified through literature research. Additionally, case study buildings are selected to evaluate the thermal performance of new materials in those buildings. Buildings are selected based on climate variation and construction types. A field survey is also conducted to get an idea about building constructional practice, material selection and user perception about thermal comfort. Detail measurements and questionnaire survey is also done at the case study building. The thermal performance of the existing building, as well as the building with new materials, is evaluated based on hourly indoor temperature and yearly thermal energy demand. Thermal mass and infiltration are passive intervention techniques applied along with NBMs. Initial results are presented in the form of variety of layer thickness and their thermal performance. Best performing wall thickness is considered for further analysis of infiltration effect.

The first case study building is selected at Dhanushadham which cooling dominant construction. Similarly, building B2 which is located at Hile is taken as the second case study building. This building is found to be heating-dominated construction with little cooling requirements during summer. The third and final case study location is at Lomanthang indicated as building B3 is a completely heating dominant building with no cooling required at all.

AAC is best suited for both Dhanushadham and Hile buildings (B1 and B2) whereas every alternative material performs more or less the same in the case of the Lomanthang building (B3). Building B1 is less improved in terms of existing load reduction as compared to building B2 and B3. Percentage reduction of yearly energy demand of building B1 ranges from 29.18% to 36.89% (minimum by PCM ceiling and maximum by AAC). In contrast, the percentage load reduction range is higher in the case of building B2 and building B3. Load reduction percentage is above 76% in building B2 and above 80% in the case of building B3. This suggests that out of all case study buildings, building B1 seems to have less improvement by applied passive solutions.

5.2 Recommendation

The scope of this research is the identification of improved building materials and calculation of the thermal performance of those materials on selected buildings. Only 6 material options including 5 wall materials and 1 roof material are considered by this research. However, other materials can also be used in Nepalese buildings. Identification of such materials and their thermal performance will generate a variety of options while moving towards energy-efficient buildings in Nepal.

Thermal performances of materials are studied only in 3 case study buildings. These buildings do not represent every climate variation and construction type of our building sector. Further study can be done based upon more variety of climates and construction types. Additionally, three case study buildings are also of different architectural design. Study of material performance incorporated in buildings with identical architectural design will provide more clarity about material applicability.

This research doesn't cover the structural stability of a building because these new materials act as a non-load bearing element of a building. Further research on the mechanical strength and structural behavior of these materials is recommended. The availability of these materials in Nepal and their cost efficiency are not studied by this research. Passive technique such as thermal mass and infiltration rate is considered at maximum beneficial point by this research. However, implementing these techniques might not be cost-effective. Hence financial and economic sustainability of these materials and passive strategies in a building construction industry needs to be studied.

Thermal mass and building airtightness are considered as two passive techniques in this research. Other passive design strategies can further aid in building thermal performance. Examples are shading, insulation, window and door glazing, etc. Study of new building materials incorporated with these techniques is recommended as the further scope of research. Additional energy-consuming sections of a building like lighting and cooking also need to be studied along with thermal improvement to enhance building overall energy efficiency.

The results presented in this research are calculated with weather file generated by means of meteonorm software leading towards errors in a result. Further research with real time monitored weather file will be more accurate.

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APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

Location:

Environment setting:

Altitude:

Temperature and Humidity:

1. What are your building dimension and orientation?

.....

2. How old is your building?

.....

3. How many rooms are there in your building and for what purpose are they used?

First Floor

Room	Dimension	Use	window size if any	Window direction	Door	Occupancy hour	Electrical utility
Room 1							
Room 2							
Room 3							
Room 4							
Room 5							

Second Floor

Room	Dimension	Use	window size if any	Window direction	Door	Occupancy hour	Electrical utility
Room 1							
Room							

2							
Room 3							
Room 4							
Room 5							

Third Floor

Room	Dimension	Use	window size if any	Window direction	Door	Occupancy hour	Electrical utility
Room 1							
Room 2							
Room 3							
Room 4							
Room 5							

Fourth Floor

Room	Dimension	Use	window size if any	Window direction	Door	Occupancy hour	Electrical utility
Room 1							
Room 2							
Room 3							
Room 4							

Room							
5							

4. Do you feel comfortable inside your house?

Season	Scale (0-7)	Time of Day	1- Extreme/ shivering cold 2- Mild cold/ chilled 3-Comfortable 4-Warmer/sweating 5-Extremely hot
Summer (indoor)			
Winter (indoor)			
Summer (outdoor)			
Winter (outdoor)			
At present			

5. How do you mitigate discomfort during the extreme season?

Summer

- AC
- Electric fan
- Consume cold beverage
- Different clothing habit
- Adjust window blind and shade
- Operating door openings inside the building (.....)
- Adjusting air vent in wall or ceiling
- Operating window (.....)
- Others

Winter

- AC
- Heater
- Consume hot beverage
- Different clothing habit
- Operating window and door
- Adjusting air vent in wall or ceiling

- Others

6. What is the main source of discomfort during summer and winter (humidity, air movement, direct sun, rigid clothing habit, etc.)

.....

7. What kind of clothes you prefer during summer and winter (0 for summer and 1 for winter)

.....

8. Do you think that your work efficiency decreases during the hot or cold season inside your house?

Yes No

9. Materials used in a building

Foundation:

Floor:

Outer wall:

Inner partition wall:

Roof:

Window:

Door:

Ceiling:

Insulation if any:

10. On what basis you designed your building and choose materials?

- traditional practices
- material availability
- contractor/ designer suggestion
- your own choice and awareness
- Others

11. Did you consult for any of the following factors while designing/constructing the building?

- orientation of a building
- applying to shade

- reduction of window
- increasing wall thickness
- any kind of insulation
- consideration of making building airtightness
- Other if any.....

12. Are you ready to retrofit your building if it makes your building comfortable? And at what cost you will do that?

Yes No

Cost affordable up to Rs...../ times of cost

Will you be ready to make the following changes to your building?

- change in building envelop
- change in internal partition
- applying to shade
- adding insulation
- removing/adding windows
- changing window/door material
- caulking and weather stripping

APPENDIX II: CONSTRUCTIONAL DETAILS OF CASE STUDY BUILDINGS

Building B1

Constructional Details of Zone 1 of B1

Element	Orientation	Area (m²)	Material
Brick Wall	East	6.14	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	Adjacent to zone 2	9.29	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	South	7.67	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	North	8.8	Brick with Plaster
Door & Window	East	3.15	Wood
Door & Window	South	1.62	Wood
Ceiling	Horizontal (External)	8.8	Concrete
Floor	Horizontal	8.8	RCC

Constructional Details of Zone 2 of B1

Element	Orientation	Area (m²)	Material
Brick Wall	Adjacent to zone 1	9.29	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	West	9.29	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	South	7	Brick with Plaster
Brick Wall	North	8.8	Brick with Plaster
Door & Window	South	1.8	Wood

Ceiling	Horizontal (External)	8.8	Concrete
Floor	Horizontal	8.8	RCC

Building B2

Element	Orientation	Area (m ²)	Material
---------	-------------	------------------------	----------

ZONE 1

Wall & Window/Door	North	11.99 & 7.65	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window	East	10.33 & 0.92	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window	West	10.33 & 0.92	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window/Door	Adjacent to Zone 2	16.95 & 2.2	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Ceiling	North 45°	19.8	GI sheet

ZONE 2

Wall & Window/Door	Adjacent to Zone 1	16.95 & 2.2	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window/Door	Adjacent to Zone 3	11.99 & 7.65	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window	East	9.44 & 0.92	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall & Window	West	9.44 & 0.92	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Ceiling	North 45° & South 45°	12.16 & 12.16	GI sheet insulated with wood from inside

ZONE 3

Wall & Window/Door	Adjacent to Zone 2	11.99 & 7.65	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Ceiling	Horizontal	19.47	GI Sheet
Wall	South	19.64	Cement Boned Stone
Wall & Window	East	3.54 & 3.10	Cement Boned Stone & Wood
Wall	West	6.64	Cement Boned Stone

Building B3

Element	Orientation	Area (m²)	Material
Wall & window/door	Northeast	9.01/5.29 & 3.34	Stone/Stone with wood insulation & wood
Wall & window/door	Southwest	9.01/5.29 & 3.34	Stone/Stone with wood insulation & wood
Wall & window/door	Northwest	47.28/28.47 & 19.8	Stone/Stone with wood insulation & wood
Wall & window/door	Southeast	47.28/28.47 & 23.44	Stone/Stone with wood insulation & wood
Floor & Ceiling	Horizontal/Adj. to Attic	202.06	Wood/Plywood

APPENDIX III: THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF NBM_s WITH DIFFERENT INFILTRATION RATES

Building B1

Figure: AAC Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: PCM Ceiling Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: PCM Drywall Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: CLT Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: Sawdust Brick Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: GB and CB Performance on B1 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: AAC Performance on B2 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: PCM Drywall Performance on B2 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: CLT Performance on B2 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: Sawdust Brick Performance on B2 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: GB and CB Performance on B2 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: AAC Performance on B3 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: PCM Drywall Performance on B3 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: CLT Performance on B3 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: Sawdust Brick Performance on B3 with Different Infiltration Rate

Figure: GB and CB Performance on B3 with Different Infiltration Rate